

D8.1 Report on the Visual Identity and Online Profile of the Project

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Project acronym	SCARBO
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SCARBOn participants

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2	Airbus Netherlands B.V.	Airbus-NL	NL
3	Absolut System SAS	Absolut	FR
4	Université Grenoble Alpes	UGA	FR
5	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	CNRS	FR
6	GRANT Garant s.r.o.	GG	CZ
7	Institut Royal d' Aéronomie Spatiale de Belgique	BIRA-IASB	BE
8	Office National d'Etudes et de Recherches Aérospatiales	ONERA	FR
9	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.	DLR	DE
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Document change record

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
CH ₄	Methane
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
L1 – L4	Levels 1 to 4 of Data Processing
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

List of reference/applicable documents

Document title	Document author	Date of issuance
Logo Manual	Grant Garant, s.r.o.	2024
D8.2 Plan of Exploitation and Dissemination of Results	Grant Garant, s.r.o.	2024

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 SCARBOn Overview

SCARBOn (Space CARBOn Observatory Next step) is an innovation action project funded under the Horizon Europe Programme. It is the continuation of the Horizon 2020 SCARBO project. SCARBOn is a multidisciplinary project carried out by a gender-diverse team, through a consortium including the space industry, SMEs and scientific institutes. It is led from Toulouse, France by Airbus Defence and Space. The SCARBOn project started in January 2024, with a total 30 months of implementation.

The main objective of the SCARBOn collaborative project is to mature the SCARBOn overall system based on a constellation of small satellites – with a miniaturised static spectrometer concept (NanoCarb) coupled with aerosol sensors (SPEXone) - that will be able to monitor greenhouse gases (GHG) – notably CO₂, and CH₄– from space. The instruments together will deliver daily accurate global measurements to monitor the diurnal variations of fossil CO₂ emissions. This CO₂ and CH₄ anthropogenic emissions monitoring data aims to be a valuable contributor to the European Commission’s endeavour to fight climate change. The monitoring data will foster the development of added-value services and will represent a state-of-the-art European alternative to the burgeoning non-European commercial initiatives.

The SCARBOn project maturation is articulated over the detailed technical definition of the NanoCarb instrument, the industrial definition of both instruments and the constellation concept confirmation, targeting an operational system availability before the end of the decade. The design of the NanoCarb instrument will be upgraded and refined following the outcomes of the previous SCARBO study, and its performances will be carefully modelled. An instrument breadboard will provide valuable data during an airborne campaign, which will be used together with modelled data to verify the instrument design. This will allow raising the instrument TRL to at least 5 by the end of the project. Furthermore, data processing at levels L1 to L4 will validate the concept capability to monitor GHG plumes from space.

1.2 Document Summary

Deliverable 8.1, under name Report on the Visual Identity and Online Profile of the Project, was produced in month six (M6) of the duration of project SCARBOn by the WP8 leader, GRANT Garant (GG).

This deliverable presents visual identity of project SCARBOn, along with the range of communication and dissemination tools that SCARBOn will use to ensure its online presence and engage its target audience. The central point of the visual identity of the project is the SCARBOn logo which directly refers to the heritage of the preceding SCARBO project. The interlinked project typography has been used to provide the consortium with Word and PowerPoint templates.

SCARBOn visual identity paves the way for clear and coherent SCARBOn online profile expressed through its website and LinkedIn profile. The online presence will be supported by other public relations materials in printed form – i.e. project fact sheet and roll-up banner destined for project communication at events, exhibitions and conferences. Finally, SCARBOn communication and dissemination of results will be boosted by final project workshop with key stakeholders, supporting further exploitation efforts.

2 Introduction

SCARBO visual identity and online presence is an important component of the project, supporting SCARBO scientific activities and boosting their impact. This document, "D8.1 Report on the Visual Identity and Online Profile of the Project," details the visual identity elements and the range of communication tools designed to secure online presence and engage SCARBO target audiences.

A unified visual identity ensures brand recognition, professionalism, and consistency across all project materials, which is essential for effective communication and dissemination. The visual identity consists of several elements – SCARBO logo and its manual for use, typography, and templates. The visual identity has been developed by the WP8 leader GRANT Garant (GG) around the SCARBO logo (which was provided to the project by the coordinator Airbus-F).

Online presence of the project is going to be secured by several communication and dissemination tools, which include the project website, LinkedIn profile, ready-to-be-printed materials such as project fact sheet and roll-up banner and press releases. Each tool is tailor-made to ensure an effective transfer of the key messages towards the SCARBO target groups (as defined within the D8.2, i.e. scientific community, policymakers and regulators, industry partners, and the local communities and general public).

A set of communication tools outlined in this document is integral to the SCARBO Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR), described in Deliverable 8.2. By maintaining a cohesive visual identity and utilizing strategically selected communication and dissemination tools, SCARBO aims to enhance its visibility, foster engagement, and ensure the successful dissemination and exploitation of its results.

3 Visual Identity

The SCARBOn project understands well the importance of presenting itself with a unified visual identity. While GG, the leader of WP 8, is in charge of developing the visual identity of SCARBOn project, all project partners were involved in the collaborative development process, allowing every consortium member to share their opinions and feedback. This ensures that SCARBOn visual identity represents the collective vision and values of the entire team.

SCARBOn is a direct successor to the SCARBO project, funded under the Horizon 2020 programme. Therefore, it was imperative for SCARBOn visual identity to be grounded on SCARBO's foundation, aiming to distinguish the projects while maintaining a clear visual connection and brand recognition.

SCARBOn's visual identity is based on the SCARBOn logo, which is further developed in the Logo Manual that presents several logo variations and defines the logo colour palette. Alongside, SCARBOn typography was defined and templates for project deliverables and presentations were produced.

All visual identity elements are available to the consortium at the project internal repository and have also been distributed via email.

3.1 SCARBOn Logo and its Manual

SCARBOn logo is a core of SCARBOn visual identity. The current SCARBOn logo is based on the design of original SCARBO logo. SCARBOn logo was initially developed and used for the project proposal. This logo was provided by the project coordinator, Airbus-F, and in the early months of the project had been adjusted by GG to better reflect the project's evolving identity and typography. The adjusted logo was presented at the kick-off meeting, where it received approval from all consortium partners.

Based on the logo, a complementary colour palette was developed. To ensure consistent application of these elements, a Logo Manual was created, serving as the foundation for the project's visual identity. This Logo Manual, included as Annex 1 of this report, details the project logo and its colour palette.

Figure 1 SCARBOn logo on white background

Figure 2 SCARBOn logo on black background

Figure 3 SCARBOn logo on colorful background

Figure 4 Colour Palette slide from the Logo Manual

3.2 Typography & Stylesheet

Recommended typography (SCARBOn styles) and a stylesheet were developed and provided for the SCARBOn consortium members. The Montserrat font was selected as the official typeface for SCARBOn. The stylesheet includes detailed instructions on how to use different SCARBOn styles within Microsoft Word documents (see Annex 2). It specifies the types of Montserrat font to use in different contexts, such as captions, paragraphs, tables, and figures, detailing variations in colour and font weight (boldness).

The stylesheet ensures consistency in visual presentation across all project materials.

Figure 5 Colour Palette slide from the Logo Manual

3.3 Templates

For SCARBOn's needs, two specific templates have been developed: a MS Word template for project deliverables, and a MS PowerPoint template for project presentations. These templates include predefined fonts and visual elements to ensure visual consistency. While the Word template primarily serves as a project deliverable template, it can be modified for other purposes as well.

Furthermore, SCARBOn Deliverable Guide, a guide for the SCARBOn project deliverables, detailing the timeline, structure, and styles for submission of project reports, was developed. It includes specific recommendations for the content and format of deliverables, such as the use of predefined templates and mandatory sections like the executive summary.

Figure 6 SCARBO n Deliverable Template

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Figure 7 SCARBO n PowerPoint Template (title and final slide)

Figure 8 SCARBOn Deliverables Guide

4 Communication Tools and Online Profile of the Project

The SCARBOn communication tools, provided by the partner GG, securing effective communication of key project messages and dissemination of its results, have been strategically chosen to effectively engage with project's target groups (see SCARBOn PEDR D8.2). These groups include the scientific community, policymakers and regulators, industry and exploitation partners, as well as the general public and local communities. By tailoring our communication efforts to the specific needs and interests of these audiences, we aim to maximize the impact and reach of the SCARBOn project.

Most SCARBOn communication tools are dedicated to the online world. The SCARBOn website serves as the central hub for all project-related information, providing regular updates on milestones, findings, and achievements. Complementing the website, SCARBOn LinkedIn profile facilitates professional networking and dialogue with stakeholders, industry professionals, and potential exploitation partners.

Alongside, project fact sheet and roll-up banner are made in a ready-to-be-printed form. The fact sheet will be available for download on the SCARBOn website. These materials of promotion are essential for outreach at conferences, events, and exhibitions, ensuring that key messages about SCARBOn's objectives and results reach their public. Additionally, our press releases will be utilized to share major project developments and findings with a wider audience, including the media and general public.

Communication tools are also an integral part of Deliverable 8.2, titled Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of the Results.

SCARBOn acknowledges its funding from the European Union and is committed to follow the visibility rules for European-funded projects. As part of this commitment, SCARBOn ensures that all communications and dissemination tools described in this document prominently display the EU emblem, funding statement and the disclaimer, demonstrating SCARBOn's alignment with the EU's guidelines and our dedication to transparency and proper attribution of support.

4.1 Websites

The SCARBOn project website, with launch planned early in M7 and available at the domain www.scarbon-project.eu, serves as the central hub for all project-related information and activities (see the structure of sub-pages in chapters 4.1.1. to 4.1.6). It is the key tool of the communication plan (detailed in Deliverable 8.2 PEDR), facilitating information flow towards the target groups. Its primary objective is to communicate essential information about the project, and updates on project findings.

Since the importance of the website for project communication was recognized, significant effort has been dedicated to the development, structure, design, and content of the website. Outlined and managed by the WP8 leader, GG, the graphical design of the website has been developed by a creative digital agency in accordance with the project's visual identity. The website structure and texts were provided by GG with inputs from all the consortium. The website preparation has been discussed lively within the consortium during monthly meetings of the SCARBOn Executive Committee.

The website is going to be launched early in M7, after several rounds of internal controls, checks, and consortium approval. At present (M6), the website is in its final phase of development. The remaining details are currently being refined, and the latest feedback

from consortium partners is being integrated. As the website is under construction, please note that all images on the website are previews. The website will be continuously updated by GG with the latest project developments.

Key visual identity elements of the EU funding are prominently displayed at the top and at the bottom of home-page and all sub-pages.

4.1.1 Homepage

The SCARBOn homepage features essential project information, including objectives, the latest news, and consortium structure. The EU funding is acknowledged by its visual elements and properly mentioned in the HP main article. The top navigation bar includes the project logo, links to various sections of the website (About, News, Consortium, Public & Media), and links to the LinkedIn profile and project-dedicated e-mail address.

Figure 9 SCARBOn HomePage Preview

Figure 10 Bottom Side of the HomePage with EU emblem, Funding Statement and the Disclaimer

4.1.2 About

The "About" page contains sub-pages on Objectives, SCARBO Heritage and Workplan. The aim of this section is to present the project in greater detail, explaining its heritage, objectives, impact and cohesive workplan.

Figure 11 SubPage About – Objectives Excerpt

4.1.3 News

The "News" section will offer the latest updates and developments related to the SCARBOn project. This will include announcements of milestones, press releases, information on current developments and results, including invitations to SCARBOn dissemination events, and many more. It serves as a hub for stakeholders and the public to stay informed about the project's ongoing activities and events in the field. Figure 12 SCARBOn Sub-page "News" with proposed layout

4.1.4 Consortium

The "Consortium" page provides information about the SCARBOn project team and is divided to sub-pages dedicated to all SCARBOn partners. Besides partners' institution promotion, each partner's role and contributions to the project are highlighted, emphasizing the collaborative effort involved in SCARBOn.

Figure 13 Sub-page Consortium, Airbus Partner's Page

4.1.5 Public & Media

The "Public & Media" page is designed to offer resources for both, the general public and media professionals. It will include different sorts of information: a downloadable fact sheet (described in chapter 4.4), press releases (chapter 4.3), and summaries of scientific results and findings from the project, ensuring transparency and public engagement.

Figure 14 Sub-page "Public&Media"

4.1.6 Other content

The website also contains other sub-pages in the lower bar, such as "Contact" page providing various means to get in touch with the SCARBOn team, or sub-pages with GDPR Statement and Imprint.

Figure 15 Lower Bar of the SCARBOn Website

4.2 LinkedIn profile

By establishing dedicated LinkedIn profile, SCARBOn seeks to communicate its objectives and achievements, updates and milestones to a broader audience, enhancing its impact and reach in relevant fields. SCARBOn LinkedIn profile is established and maintained by GG.

It seeks to engage industry professionals and potential exploitation partners, as well as the public, and foster a network of stakeholders interested in climate data and space research.

SCARBOn's LinkedIn activity is planned to increase, with posts being coordinated alongside the website launch in early M7. The launch of the website will be announced on the profile, and the link to the website will be added to the LinkedIn profile.

SCARBOn's LinkedIn, named SCARBOn - Space CARBon Observatory next step, can be accessed under this link:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/scarbon-project/>.

On LinkedIn, hashtag #SCARBOn will be utilized in posts, along with HaDEA's hashtags #HorizonEU #EUSpaceResearch #EUSpace.

Figure 16 SCARBOn LinkedIn Profile

4.3 Press-release

The SCARBOn project will use press releases for its communication and dissemination efforts. We plan to issue at least two press releases during the project: one at the beginning in M 7 to announce the project launch (time of release is coordinated also with project's website launch), and another in month 27, near the project's conclusion, to highlight its outcomes and achievements. SCARBOn press releases are produced and distributed by GG in close cooperation with the SCARBOn EXCOM.

Upon approval of the EXCOM, the press release will be published on SCARBOn website and actively disseminated to selected audience.

4.4 Fact sheet

SCARBOn Fact sheet is a concise, visually appealing document designed to provide a quick overview of the project. It provides key information about the SCARBOn project, highlighting its objectives, technological innovations, and anticipated impacts in a visually attractive, simplified way. It features short descriptions of the project's main instruments, NanoCarb and SPEXone, which are designed for high-accuracy detection of CO₂ and CH₄ emissions. The factsheet is currently under development, waiting for final approval of the consortium. Once completed, it will be available on the website as a ready-to-print trifold flyer, ensuring easy access for all types of audience. Project consortium will be simultaneously provided printed copies of the fact sheet for dissemination at events and conferences etc.

Figure 17 SCARBOn Fact Sheet (draft preview)

4.5 Roll-up banner

A project roll-up banner is currently being developed under the supervision of GG, in close cooperation with all consortium partners. Roll-up banner will play an important role in promoting SCARBO n at various events and exhibitions. It will be designed in a ready-to-print format (in size 80cm by 200 cm), making it easy for consortium members to download from the SCARBO n internal project repository.

Figure 18 SCARBO n Roll- Up banner (draft preview)

4.6 Project Workshop

At the end of the project (month 30) a remote SCARBO n workshop will be organised by GG to present the main SCARBO n achievements to the key selected stakeholders, while building on the SCARBO n professional links.

Final Workshops will serve as a communication and dissemination tool in several ways. The workshops will promote the SCARBO n project results, such as the outcomes of airborne campaigns, NanoCarb instrument performance, and the effectiveness of the SCARBO n constellation system, through detailed presentations and discussions. Additionally, by inviting key stakeholders, the workshops will foster collaborations and synergies, enhancing the impact and future exploitation of the project outcomes and supporting the integration of SCARBO n's advancements into broader GHG monitoring initiatives.

It will be a crucial communication and dissemination tool aimed at engaging a wide range of key stakeholders.

5 Conclusion

The development of a unified visual identity and a robust online profile for the SCARBOn project is essential for achieving effective project communication and dissemination of its results. By establishing a consistent visual identity, SCARBOn enhances its brand recognition and engagement with various stakeholders. The comprehensive set of communication tools developed, including the project website, LinkedIn profile, info-flyer, roll-up banner, and press releases, ensures that key messages are effectively delivered to the target audiences.

As SCARBOn progresses, these communication strategies will play a pivotal role in promoting the project's objectives, sharing its innovative advancements, and fostering collaboration with industry partners and stakeholders. The visual identity not only represents the collective vision and values of the SCARBOn team but also strengthens the project's visibility and impact within the scientific and industrial communities. The continued effort to update and refine these communication tools will support the successful dissemination and exploitation of SCARBOn's results, contributing to the broader goal of advancing space-based GHG monitoring and mitigating climate change.

Annex 1 Logomanual

Annex 2 Stylesheet

SCARBOn
SPACE CARBON OBSERVATORY *next step*

Logomanual

SCARBO
SPACE CARBON OBSERVATORY **next step**

01
SCARBOn Logo

SCARB
SPACE CARBON OBSERVATORY **next step**

Logo on a white background

02

Logo on Background

SCARBOn
SPACE CARBON OBSERVATORY **next step**

Logo on a full color background

03

Logo on Background

SCARB
SPACE CARBON OBSERVATORY next step

Logo on a full color background

04

Logo on Background

● 100 %

● 60 % opacity

Logo on a white background

05

Applicable only if outcome is in B&W or with prevailing shades of grey

SCARBOn
SPACE CARBON OBSERVATORY next step

● 100 %

SCARBOn
SPACE CARBON OBSERVATORY next step

○ 40 % opacity

Logo on a dark background

06
Applicable only if outcome is in B&W or with prevailing shades of grey

Print

Online

08
Minimum Size

✓ Correct

✗ Incorrect

R 17
G 237
B 137

R 55
G 62
B 72

10
Color Palette

Annex 2

STYLE SHEET

SCARBOn Section Title

1 SCARBOn Heading1

1.1 SCARBOn Heading2

1.1.1 SCARBOn Heading3

SCARBOn Normal Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

SCARBOn Normal BOLD SCARBOn Normal BOLD SCARBOn Normal BOLD

Figure 1 NAME - SCARBOn_Figures headings

Figure 2 NAME

Figure 3 NAME

SCARBOn_Figures texts

Table 1 NAME - SCARBOn_Tables headings

Table 2 NAME

Table 3 NAME

SCARBOn_Tables texts

Table 4 NAME

Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4
SCARBOn text			
Content			
Content			

Source

2 How to use Figures and Tables

When you want to insert a new Figure/Table, a picture, chart and similar follow these steps.

1. Insert a picture / table
2. In a place where a caption of the figure/table is needed click on **References** in the menu and chose **Insert Caption**

3. Dialog box opens
4. Choose Label: Figure/Table
5. The caption will be automatically numbered
6. Enter Name of the Figure/Table
7. Click OK

8. To update a Table of Figures/Tables right click Table of Figures
9. Choose Update Field
10. Choose Update entire Table

3 Landscape layout

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

- Insert section break
- Change layout to landscape
- To adjust page numbering
 - o Go to Header and Footer Design tools
 - o Right click page number in the footer
 - o Choose Format page number
 - o Choose appropriate selection

